

USE OF GRAPHENE TO REDUCE RESIN CURE SHRINKAGE

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ABSTRACT

The effects of graphene on resin cure shrinkage was studied via measurement of change in volume of a tetrafunctional epoxy resin, which was cured at high temperature. The method of measurement was analysed and determined to be sufficient for small changes in volume as observed in this study. The performance of the neat resin was compared with graphene-filled resins of 0.30 wt% and 0.60 wt% by weight. In addition, DSC was used to thermally analyse the three different resins and quantify the heat of reaction, while Raman spectroscopy was used to determine the distribution of graphene in the resin after blending. The relationship between graphene content and dispersion on resin cure shrinkage was investigated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Component deformation develops from induced residual stresses in the composite during curing. They result from a combination of two main factors, namely the thermal expansion mismatch between the fibre and the matrix, and resin shrinkage of the matrix during curing [1]. Current methods of mitigation involve careful control of processing conditions and modification of the tool, however these practices are costly in terms of resources and time. Hence, it is desirable to reduce this effect and some studies have successfully shown the benefits of adding graphene or other similar nanomaterials into a polymer matrix [2,3].

Sum [2] has shown that while studies like Sinha *et al.* [3] demonstrate the improvements in reduction of shrinkage with more nanomaterial fillers, the aspect ratio of the fillers is also a main factor. The author studied the diametrical shrinkage of a room temperature cure epoxy using 0.20 wt% of graphene with different aspect ratios. Higher aspect ratios gave significantly more reduction (up to 41%) in diametrical shrinkage.

In the present work the use of graphene flakes to reduce resin shrinkage in a low-shrinkage resin is studied. The efficacy of graphene to reduce the cure shrinkage is investigated for different filler percentages in a tetrafunctional epoxy resin, which is cured at high temperature. Concurrently this study also assesses a method to accurately quantify cure volume shrinkage of epoxies. Challenges in obtaining reliable data is particularly true for low-shrinkage epoxies because small deviations or noises could influence the observations significantly. Using Gauge R&R analysis, the efficacy of the method is determined. Thermal analysis and Raman spectroscopy are also used to study the characteristics of the resin when enhanced with graphene.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

MY9512, a tetra-functional high temperature cure epoxy resin is used in this study, with DF50EP as the hardener, UR500 as the accelerator and some cab-o-sil fillers for stability of the blend. The ratio, by weight for the resin blend is MY9512: DF50EP: UR500: Cab-o-sil = 50:5:1:1.

For blends with graphene, graphene content is the weight percentage of graphene in the total resin blend. 0.30 wt% and 0.60 wt% are considered in this study. The graphene used has flake thickness of approximately 1 to 2 nm and aspect ratio (*i.e.* flake length to thickness ratio) ranging approximately 250 to 500.

The components of the resin are mixed together in a planetary mixer at 2000 rpm and at 20 kPa vacuum pressure for 3 minutes. This is done for 3 cycles. For the blends with graphene, graphene and the resin are mixed together first, followed by the addition of the other three components. Together the whole blend is similarly mixed as for the case without graphene.

2.2 Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Measurements

DSC is used for thermal analysis of the different resin blends: neat, 0.30 wt% graphene, and 0.60 wt% graphene. Samples weighing approximately 6.5 – 15.0 mg are encapsulated in hermetically sealed aluminium pans and tested dynamically between 32 to 250°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min in Nitrogen. The heat of reaction is obtained from the tests, as well as peak temperature. Immediately after the run, another test is run on the same samples from 0 to 250°C to check for residual curing.

2.3 Raman Imaging

The resin blends are scanned using Raman spectroscopy to determine the distribution of graphene in the resin system. Thin flat films of resin samples are prepared on glass slides. A 633 nm red laser is used to map several regions of the samples. Scans are made for the neat and graphene-filled resin blends. Identification of graphene in the Raman maps are based on the D-band and G-band peaks typically seen in graphene spectra.

2.4 Volumetric Shrinkage Measurements

Volumetric shrinkage of the resin samples is determined with a gas pycnometer (Figure 1), using Helium gas. The resin samples are prepared in small 3.3 cm³ aluminium cups. Each cup is filled to about 1.8 to 2.2 g of resin, as shown in Figure 2 for neat and graphene-filled resin samples.

The gas pycnometer is calibrated and a standard is measured for confirmation before the experiments. The volume is measured with run precision whereby for each sample, at least 5 runs are made and the results are accepted once the sample volumes for the 4 most recent previous runs fall within 0.00099 cm³ of the sample volume of the current run. In addition, A Gauge R&R analysis is conducted before the experiments to identify the contribution of measurement system variations. This is done using six uncured samples, with one repetition and two operators.

The volume of each resin sample is measured before and after curing. The resin is cured following the three-step temperature-duration profile shown in Figure 3. After curing, the oven is turned off and the samples are allowed to cool down to about 90°C before being removed from the oven to rapidly cool outside. Samples need to be at room temperature (32 ± 1°C) before the volume is measured. It is important to note that the samples are randomised for measurement to avoid biasing. Each sample is also measured twice to ensure repeatability in the measured volumes.

Figure 1: Gas pycnometer.

Figure 2: Neat (top row) and graphene-filled resin samples in aluminium cups.

Figure 3: Cure profile used for all the resin samples.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 DSC Analysis

The results of the dynamic scanning measurements are shown in Figure 4. There are two distinct peaks for the neat resin, suggesting two main reactions occurring during cure. With the addition of graphene, the two peaks seem to be merging, thus appearing much less distinguishable in the spectrum. The second cycle of 0 to 250°C is not shown here, but indicates no residual cure for all three resin samples. Hence, they have all been fully cured during the first cycle.

Table 1 summarises the peak temperature and heat of reaction of the neat and graphene-filled resin samples. The heat of reaction is normalised by the weight of each respective sample to facilitate meaningful comparison between the different samples. Resin sample with 0.60 wt% graphene has the lowest peak temperature (154.97°C) and heat of reaction (577.08 J/g). Figure 5 shows for each resin blend, the comparison of means for heat of reaction (bars) and peak temperature (curve), with the standard deviations shown. It is evident that the graphene-filled blends have significantly lower mean heat of reaction (>7% reduction), but doubling the graphene content from 0.30 wt% to 0.60 wt% did not give any significant difference.

The general observation is the decrease in peak temperature and heat of reaction with the addition of graphene content. This could be due to the effect of graphene - an efficient thermal conductor - more efficiently distributing the heat for curing hence aiding the resin system reaction.

Figure 4: Rate of heat generation from dynamic scanning experiments.

Figure 5: Heat of reaction (bars) and peak temperature (curve) for the different resin samples.

3.2 Raman Spectroscopy

A representative Raman spectrum of the graphene-filled resin samples, in red, is shown in Figure 6. It shows three distinct peaks corresponding to approximately 1330, 1583 and 1614 cm^{-1} . The third is a prominent peak observed even in the neat resin spectrum, while, as shown by the blue curve which represents the graphene component, 1330 cm^{-1} is the D-band and 1583 cm^{-1} is the G-band for graphene [4].

Figure 7 is the result of Raman spectra mapping over an area of the resin blends with 0.30 wt% and 0.60 wt% graphene. By separating the components in the spectra and highlighting the regions with high D- and G-bands, the graphene and the resin matrix components could be delineated. This mapping is done on several different locations and all show a similar distribution. Figure 7(a) clearly shows graphene is well-distributed in the 0.30 wt% samples. Figure 7(b), on the hand, shows the presence of agglomerations in the 0.60 wt% samples, as evident by the large brighter regions. Similar observations of increased agglomeration with graphene loading have been reported by other workers [5]. This agglomeration of graphene could result in inefficiencies, which will be discussed in the following section.

Figure 6: Raman spectra of a graphene-filled resin sample (red), showing the 3 distinct peaks, and of the graphene component (blue).

Figure 7: Maps of Raman spectrum of graphene-filled resin samples: (a) 0.30 wt%, and (b) 0.60wt%. Graphene is depicted as the brighter regions.

3.3 Volumetric Shrinkage

Through a Gauge R&R analysis of gas pycnometer measurements of the samples, individual measurements are expected to vary by $\pm 0.004719 \text{ cm}^3$, which is three times the standard deviation. This is the measurement system variation (MSV) for 99.73% of the population of samples, assuming a normal distribution. Hence, in order for the pycnometer to detect differences in volume between uncured and cured resin, the cure volume shrinkage needs to be larger than the MSV. Figure 8 is a plot of change in volume of samples compared to the MSV (dashed line). All values are above 0.004719 cm^3 , so the shrinkage of the samples in this study is within the detectable limit. Values below the MSV would be taken as not significantly high and thus considered as zero shrinkage.

Figure 9 is a comparison of mean volumetric shrinkage percentage (with standard deviation) of neat, 0.30 wt% and 0.60 wt% resins. Both graphene-filled resins show significantly lower volumetric shrinkage compared to the neat resin. The percentage shrinkage reduction compared to neat resin is shown by the curve. Graphene reduced the volumetric shrinkage of the resin significantly, by at least 39%, based on mean comparison.

While it is clear that graphene reduces the shrinkage of the resin, there appears to be a threshold content above which no appreciable benefit is achieved. Based on the two graphene-filled samples considered in this study, when the content of graphene is doubled from 0.30 wt% to 0.60 wt%, there is no significant reduction in volumetric shrinkage. At 0.60 wt%, the mean volumetric shrinkage is slightly reduced, but the variation between samples is large. This observation could be referred back to the Raman mapping shown above. While the 0.30 wt% resin has good distribution, the 0.60 wt% resin has a lot of agglomerates. Hence, despite having more graphene content, the poor distribution did not allow this to be fully exploited. This is further supported by the large sample variation in volumetric shrinkage. The 0.60%-filled resin has a standard deviation more than three times that of the 0.30%-filled resin.

Improving the dispersion could improve the shrinkage behavior of the resin. However, at higher graphene content, this would require solution mixing and an efficient way of extracting the solvent because traces of solvent in the resin could influence the mechanical properties of nanocomposites [6].

Figure 8: Change in volume of samples used in Gauge R&R analysis. Dashed line is the measurement system variation.

Figure 9: Mean volumetric shrinkage percentage (with standard deviation) of neat, 0.30 wt% and 0.60 wt% resins. Percentage shrinkage reduction is shown by the curve.

4 CONCLUSION

The use of graphene to reduce resin cure shrinkage has been studied for 0.30% and 0.60% graphene content by weight. On average, at least 39% volumetric shrinkage reduction is achieved. DSC measurements show that graphene reduces the heat of reaction and peak temperature. The peaks representing two main reactions in the resin system are also observed to merge with a gradual transition. Being a good thermal conductor, it is believed that graphene more efficiently distributes the heat for curing hence aiding the resin system reaction. This in turn reduces the amount of shrinkage.

It has been shown that the distribution of graphene in the resin plays an important role. The dispersion has been studied using Raman spectroscopy and mapping, via separation of the components in the spectra to highlight the regions with high D- and G-bands that represent graphene. It is observed that good dispersion for the 0.30 wt% resin performs as well as the relatively poorly dispersed, but higher graphene content, 0.60 wt% resin.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Fernlund, N. Rahman, R. Courdji M. Bresslauer, A.Poursartip, K.Willden and K.Nelson. Experimental and numerical study of the effect of cure cycle, tool surface, geometry, and lay-up on the dimensional fidelity of autoclave-processed composite parts. *Composites A*, **33** (3), 341 (2002).
- [2] W.S. Sum, Reduced Shrinkage of Epoxies with Graphene. *11th Asian-Australasian Conference on Composite Materials, Cairns, 29th July - 1st August, 2018*.
- [3] S. Sinha, J. Shetty, C. Nair and L. Lakshmikanth. Effect of Carbon Nanotubes and Graphene on The Polymerization Shrinkage of Heat Cure Acrylic Resin. *Trends in Prosthodontics and Dental Implantology (TPDI)*, **5**(2), 2014, pp 31-35.
- [4] L.M. Malard, M.A. Pimenta, G. Dresselhaus and M.S. Dresselhaus. Raman spectroscopy in graphene. *Physics Reports*, **473**, 51 (2009).
- [5] Z. Lia, J. Chua, C. Yang, S. Hao, M.A. Bissett, I.A. Kinloch, R.J. Young. Effect of functional groups on the agglomeration of graphene in nanocomposites. *Composites Science and Technology*, **163**, 116 (2018).
- [6] L.-C. Tang, Y.-J. Wan, D. Yan, Y.-B. Pei, L. Zhao, Y.-B. Li, L.-B. Wu, J.-X. Jiang, G.-Q. Lai. The effect of graphene dispersion on the mechanical properties of graphene/epoxy composites. *Carbon*, **60**, 16 (2013).